

Studies in Quinoline Compounds. Part V.

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In our previous communications we prepared the simple substitution products of 8-aminoquinolines. The present paper deals with certain aminoisopropyl derivatives of 8-aminoquinolines. The characteristic feature of these compounds is that there is an asymmetric carbon atom in the side-chain which is also a speciality of plasmochin. In short, these compounds can be looked upon as the lower homologues of plasmochin which, as it is understood, is an aminoisopentyl derivative of 8-aminoquinoline.

In the successive condensation of β -bromopropylphthalimide which was obtained in good yield by a modification of Seitz's method (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 2624), with 8-aminoquinoline or its derivatives, we have followed the method of Baldwin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 2962). In this case the time for condensing the β -bromopropylphthalimide was considerable, in some cases nearly 24 hours being needed for the completion of the reaction. The successive action of hydrazine in boiling alcoholic solution and hydrochloric acid on the resulting 8- β -phthalamidoisopropylaminoquinolines, effected, as was found by Baldwin, a smooth hydrolysis and the dihydrochlorides of compounds of the nature of 8- β -aminoisopropylaminoquinoline were easily isolated. In this way we have prepared the following compounds:

- (1) 8- β -Aminoisopropylaminoquinoline.
- (2) 8- β -Aminoisopropylamino-6-methylquinoline.
- (3) 8- β -Aminoisopropylamino-6-methoxyquinoline.
- (4) 8- β -Aminoisopropylamino-6-ethoxyquinoline.

The free bases are generally uncrystallisable and therefore we have not isolated them. The bihydrochlorides are solids which can be easily crystallised from absolute alcohol. These dissolve very easily in water giving rise to a faintly acidic solution. The alkylation of these compounds is not very difficult, but the products cannot be obtained in a very pure state.

For the sake of comparison we have also prepared the (1) 8- β -aminoethylaminoquinoline, (2) 8- β -aminopropylaminoquinoline.

We would point out here that the condensation of β -bromopropylphthalimide can only be effected with 8-aminoquinoline and its derivatives, whereas the isomeric 6-, 7-, or 5-aminoquinolines cannot be made to undergo this condensation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

8- β -Aminoisopropylaminoquinoline,

The starting materials are β -bromopropylphthalimide and 8-aminoquinoline, of which the former is prepared by heating allylphthalimide (6 g.) with fuming hydrobromic acid (d 1.78, 10 c.c.) for about 10 minutes on a boiling water-bath and then pouring into water. The solid thus separated is then crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 150°.

β -Bromopropylphthalimide (5 g.) is intimately mixed with 8-aminoquinoline (3 g.) and heated on an oil-bath at 125-35° for about 24 hours, when the separation of the solid hydrobromide is nearly complete. The nearly solid mixture is then stirred up with absolute alcohol and filtered. The precipitate is washed thoroughly with alcohol and dried in vacuum, yield 4 g.

The above hydrobromide (4 g.) is suspended in absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) and 1.5 c.c. (2.5 mols.) of hydrazine hydrate added into it. The mixture is heated on the water-bath for 1½ to 2 hours. The alcohol is then driven off and the white spongy residue is mixed with an excess of 2*N*-hydrochloric acid and heated on a boiling water-bath for 15 minutes. The precipitated phthalylhydrazide is filtered off and the filtrate basified. The base is taken up with chloroform. On passing dry hydrogen chloride into the dry chloroform solution, the bihydrochloride is precipitated, and is recrystallised from absolute alcohol. It is a brownish yellow solid, easily soluble in water, m.p. 235°. The solution is only faintly acidic. (Found: N, 15.5. $C_{12}H_{17}N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 15.3 per cent.).

8-β-Aminoisopropylamino-6-methylquinoline.—The preparation of this compound is almost the same as the previous one. The separation of the intermediate hydrobromide is nearly complete within 12 hours. The bihydrochloride is a brownish yellow solid melting at 255°. It is very easily soluble in water, moderately soluble in absolute alcohol from which it is recrystallised. (Found: N, 14.3. $C_{13}H_{19}N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 14.6 per cent.).

8-β-Aminoisopropylamino-6-methoxyquinoline is prepared from β-bromopropylphthalimide (4 g.) and 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline (2.5 g.). It is a yellow solid melting at 221°. (Found: N, 13.7. $C_{13}H_{19}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 13.8 per cent.).

8-β-Aminoisopropylamino-6-ethoxyquinoline melts at 231° (Found: N, 13.0. $C_{14}H_{21}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 13.2 per cent.).

8-β-Aminoethylaminoquinoline,

It is prepared from 8-aminoquinoline and β-bromoethylphthalimide. It melts at 241°. (Found: N, 16.4. $C_{11}H_{15}N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 16.3 per cent.).

8-γ-Aminopropylaminoquinoline.—It is obtained as above from 8-aminoquinoline and γ-bromopropylphthalimide. It melts at 247°. (Found: N, 15.5. $C_{12}H_{17}N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 15.3 per cent.).

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Received August 17, 1931.

